

Data Management Handbook

NASA EPSCoR Snow Albedo Project

Version 0.8 - 2025 June

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	3
SECTION 1: CURRENT CONTEXT IN THE RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT ECOSYSTEM	4
CURRENT FEDERAL, FUNDING AGENCY, AND LOCAL RESEARCH DATA POLICY SUMMARY	4
<i>Federal policy and funding agency guidance</i>	4
<i>University policy context</i>	5
<i>NASA EPSCoR Snow Albedo DMP</i>	5
<i>Research Data Stewardship and Collaboration Agreements</i>	6
REPOSITORIES.....	6
PUBLISHERS & DATA POLICY	7
RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT GOALS: REPRODUCIBILITY, REPLICABILITY, TRANSPARENCY, QUALITY, INTEGRITY, AND FAIR	8
SECTION 2: APPLIED RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT.....	8
PHYSICAL DATA STORAGE	8
ORGANIZATION.....	9
DATA PIPELINES	10
METADATA	11
LICENSING AND PUBLIC DOMAIN WAIVERS (<i>I.E.</i> , INTELLECTUAL RIGHTS).....	12
DATA INTEGRITY	13
DATA MODELING	14
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	15
APPENDIX I: POLICY AND GUIDANCE REFERENCES	16

Executive Summary

The purpose of this Data Management Handbook, or DMH, is to serve as a curatorial tool to a) implement data management best practices; and b) to document decision points as data producers actively manage their data toward data sharing and reuse. The DMH is thus designed to be used primarily by researchers, and to serve as a starting point in opening doors for researchers and data curators to collaborate, critically examine, and document data management practices on a project-by-project basis.

As such, this instantiation of the DMH is both generalizable to other projects and written to speak to the needs of the NASA EPSCoR Cooperative Award entitled *A transdisciplinary approach to assess measurements of albedo across snowy landscapes using multiple sensors at multiple scales*, or, in shorthand for project members, the NASA EPSCoR Snow Albedo Project.

*Version note: This version of the DMH, version 0.8, is a work in progress. The DOI for Version 0.8 is **10.5281/zenodo.15671244**. The forthcoming Version 1.0 will address known issues including missing links and references, and will likewise be archived on Zenodo.*

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronyms and abbreviations used in this document may be defined here.

Acronym	Abbreviation for
AGU	American Geophysical Union
DOI	digital object identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
PURL	persistent uniform resource locator
URL	uniform resource locator

Section 1: Current context in the research data management ecosystem

Section task: Create an Appendix of references pointing to current federal, funding agency, and local research data policy. Also refer to relevant disciplinary community guidance such as the AGU Author Guidelines¹, and relevant literature including the FAIR principles. Summarize policy and guidance documents in each relevant section, and extract 4-6 key points to summarize at the head of the section. For URL-based references where no digital object identifier (DOI) exists, point to or create persistent uniform resource locators (PURLs) via Internet Archive's Wayback Machine² to improve documentation accessibility. Create a separate Appendix of definitions to clarify any uncertain terms used in this document. Define acronyms and abbreviations in the list included in the front matter of this document.

Assessment of completion

You create a useful policy reference document with full citation information.

Current federal, funding agency, and local research data policy summary

Objective: make connections between federal and local policy documents, the project DMP, dynamic planning, and DMP implementation tasks, and then link those connections back to the project domains' research processes. Summarize here.

Federal policy and funding agency guidance

For U.S.-based projects, provide a short summary of current U.S.-centric research data policies including federal mandates (e.g., OSTP's 2022 Nelson Memo and 2013 Holdren Memo) and funding agency requirements (e.g., NASA general DM policy and LANDSAT-specific guidance) that apply to the current research project. Give examples (minimum: 3) of what steps team members could take to operationalize current mandate(s) within the scope and context of the current research project.

For international projects, provide references and summarize participating countries' federal and funding agency data policies.

¹ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250616015856/https://www.agu.org/publications/authors/journals/data-software-for-authors#needed#guidance>

² <https://web.archive.org/>. The "Save Page Now" function can be used to create PURLs for webpages that are not already archived in the Internet Archive collection.

Assessment of completion

The federal-to-local policy summary thoughtfully references policy documents, peer-reviewed literature, and community guidelines, and includes at minimum three steps project members can take to integrate mandates into project work.

Implementation: data product tasks

Use federal and funding agency policy documents as a reference for project data product decision-making procedures and document the decision-making process here over the course of the project.

University policy context

Using MSU Electronic Research Data Policy (^3) write a brief statement about what project members need to do to be in compliance with University policy for this project.

Assessment of completion

Accurately capture the salient points of the policy in your statement.

Implementation: data product tasks

Use MSU Electronic Research Data Policy (^3) as a reference for project data product decision-making procedures and document the decision-making process here.

NASA EPSCoR Snow Albedo DMP

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are living documents eligible for changes throughout a project. Include the NASA EPSCoR Snow Albedo DMP (^1) in an appendix to this DMH. Review the document against current NASA data management guidelines – these may have changed since the project proposal stage -- and note where changes to the DMP may be useful (for discussion with the team).

Assessment of completion

Include the correct documentation with references to appendices in your Table of Contents. Identify whether the current DMP is meeting both team needs (e.g., for data product compatibility with LANDSAT data) and NASA guidance. Identify at minimum one relevant DMP statement per each of the NASA DMP requirements listed in the guidelines. Document whether the project DMP statements are still accurate and relevant to the team

goals, and that they align with other (e.g., local) policy, if applicable. Indicate areas that require clarification.

Implementation: data product tasks

On at minimum a yearly basis, use the NASA EPSCoR DMP (^1) as reference for team data product decision-making procedures and document the decision-making process here. If guidance is missing or unclear in the DMP, improve the relevant plan section.

Research Data Stewardship and Collaboration Agreements

Research Data Stewardship Agreements (RDSAs) and Collaboration Agreements (CAs) can be developed for a project to clarify what research products the team intends to create; who has an interest in authorship/creatorship of research products; who the planned authors are intended to be; and the process and/or criteria to become an author of a research product. Include template RDSA (^4) and CA (^5) documents in a DMH appendix, for further discussion with the team.

Assessment of completion

Include the correct documentation with references to appendices in your Table of Contents. Discuss the documents and their use with the team.

Implementation: data product tasks

Use the Research Data Stewardship Agreement (RDSA) (^4) and Collaboration Agreement (CA) (^5) documents as reference for project decision-making procedures and document the decision-making process within those documents.

Repositories

Data repositories preserve data ultimately for future reuse. Reusability assessment is the subject of the Implementation task of this subsection. While completing that task, answer the following: Which of the CURATE(D) criteria were most useful in your assessment? What other criteria might the team use to determine if the data could be reused as intended? Document the answers to these questions in this summary area, and in the spirit of answering, "How do we evaluate research data for reusability?"

Assessment of completion

Create a thoughtful procedure and/or checklist outlining key points of reusability assessment, and demonstrating application of concepts to the project research context.

Implementation: data product tasks

The NASA EPSCoR Snow Albedo project will use the NASA Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) DAAC to preserve data products generated on the project. Use the "Check" and "Understand" steps from the CURATE(D) checklist (^15) to review existing project data products (i.e., metadata/documentation, code, Jupyter Notebooks, data files, etc.). How effective are the metadata/documentation and other files in conveying the content and purpose of the datasets to others on the project who are not familiar with them? How accessible are the file formats? Would others be able to reuse these data in an analysis, or would they need further input and/or documentation?

Publishers & Data Policy

Create a procedure to document the steps you took in the subsequent Implementation tasks of this subsection to create a Data Availability Statement (DAS) and Data Citation (DC). Integrate recommendations from the data availability assessment task. Cite the resources you used.

Assessment of completion

Create a thoughtful procedure demonstrating application of concepts. Cite resources used. Reflect: would your lab mate be able to use this procedure to generate a DAS and DC?

Implementation: data product tasks

Use the AGU Author Guidelines (^11 - ref) to create a Data Availability Statement (DAS) and Data Citation (DC) for a project research data product. (For the data citation, you may also want to refer to the EDI Five Phases... (^6): Phase 5: Cite... page.)

Data availability assessment: choose a recent journal article relevant to your research (does not need to be published by AGU) and determine: can you access the data and/or software that support the results? Does the author make a data availability statement? How might your findings inform project data policy on subject of DASs and DCs?

Assessment of completion

Create a DAS and a DC according to AGU or EDI guidelines.

For the Data availability assessment task, note where you checked for the data and software. If failing to find data from the first article, try another article. Discuss your recommendations related to DASs and DCs.

Research Data Management Goals: Reproducibility, replicability, transparency, quality, integrity, and FAIR

After completing the subsequent implementation tasks for this subsection, create three milestones (concrete, achievable, measurable benchmarks that may require many actionable items) for project data management work: align each goal with a different RDM goal. What steps would you recommend to make project data and workflows more reproducible/replicable, transparent, or higher quality?

Assessment of completion

Create a minimum of three milestones. Recommend concrete actions for the project team to take to align with FAIR data principles and data management goals.

Implementation: data product tasks

The NASA EPSCoR Snow Albedo DMP (^{ref}) is written to meet the NASA DMP requirements (²: Figure 2). It is also written to move project data toward the FAIR data principles (⁹) and other practices that support the RDM goals of reproducibility / replicability, transparency, and quality, among others. How do you see these goals reflected in the DMP? Identify one statement from the DMP that could serve in support of each of reproducibility/replicability, transparency, and quality. Reflect on how the FAIR data principles and RDM goals can be integrated into project data product development.

Assessment of completion

Identify multiple statements in support of the three goals, making links between implementation actions and the goals they support. Develop a few recommendations for how to make project data more FAIR and in line with other named RDM goals.

Section 2: Applied Research Data Management

Physical Data Storage

Organization

As you apply the project file naming schema in the associated Implementation task below, annotate the file naming schema as needed to document any additional Identifiers and/or any changes you would suggest. Store the annotated file naming schema with your data files, and reference it here in relation to the project data product with which it is associated. Reference any other documentation you use.

Assessment of completion

Document any deviations from the standard project file naming schema that you use. Store your annotated version of the schema with your data product. Cite your references.

Implementation: data product tasks

Apply the project file naming schema (^ref – include as Appendix: Spectra_metadata_ex-vbEdits.xlsx) to your data product files (i.e., data, scripts, Jupyter Notebooks, visualizations, etc.). Review and correct any additional data reusability issues that relate to file names, file formats, special characters, and/or data types. For reference, use as needed the File naming schema (^13a (see pp. 3-5 starting with "2. File and Data Product Directory Naming schema"); EDI Organize and Clean steps (^6); Excel Data Curation Primer (^14), and CURATE(D) Checklist Check and Understand steps (^15). Correct data files programmatically, and always keep original files separate from corrected files. If any data files are modified manually, write a precise and descriptive list of the operations you perform on this dataset to bring it in line with standards and keep the list of modifications with your dataset. Ensure that code or scripts all use relative path names, and that all files called within code or scripts are present with the data product in order to prevent file dependency errors.

Assessment of completion

Consistently apply the project file naming schema to your data product files. Identify and correct data reusability issues. You fully document each correction by naming the problem (e.g., removal of special characters from column headers), how you fixed it, and references used (documentation can be in the form of code and related annotations).

Data pipelines

Data pipelines, otherwise known as serialization, are well known in long-standing big data- and data science-related fields, but less known in domains with historically smaller data sets. The objective of using a data pipeline structure is to organize and retain the order of operations and connections between the objects of analysis (e.g., raw data, scripts, protocols, visualizations, analysis-ready data, etc.).

As you are completing the associated implementation tasks below on your current datasets, document the steps you would need to take to integrate the pipeline structure earlier in the research process with a future project or dataset. Include references to additional documentation that you use in your process (e.g., the data pipeline format (^13a)).

Assessment of completion

Create a thoughtful procedure for future use that demonstrates application of concepts. Include detailed steps. Cite resources used. Reflect: would your lab mate be able to use your procedure to implement the pipeline structure at the inception of a different data product on this project?

Implementation: data product tasks

Using an existing project data product, first, make a copy of the full set of files that you will be working with and store it separately from the original. With the copied files, begin by organizing into data pipeline format (^13a, ^13b) the following: your raw data; code/computational Excel/operational protocols; intermediary data; analytical data; and metadata. If you don't have all of the above-listed files, create placeholder README text files with descriptive file names and containing a cursory sentence or two description of what the file represents (e.g., canonical protocol files that are stored elsewhere; or files you expect to be creating as you prepare data for data analysis), as a reminder of files required to complete your data product. Place the files where they would go in the pipeline file structure. There may be duplicate or intermediary-step files that are unnecessary to keep – set these aside in a separate folder for later review with the data creator (even if that is you). The analysis-ready data file should be in .csv format if tabular, or if otherwise, in one of the formats referenced in the nsidc-daac-data-accession-request-form / Data Formats section. When you and/or the project data creator (if not you) are satisfied with the new file organization structure and confident that all original files flagged for preservation are present, the original data files / structure can be archived short term with a note to indicate a date of deletion (referencing things in their original organizational structure is sometimes necessary).

Protocols and methods files often benefit from special consideration. Consider any field- or lab-protocols you may use/have used in collecting/generating project data (it is

unnecessary to include data analysis protocols at this point unless they are available; for now, just include data generation procedures, if available). Ensure all data generation-related protocols used / expected to be used (to the best of current knowledge) are either included or referenced in the pipeline structure.

The goal of these tasks is to begin to create the structure and/or mental cues that will enable others (even future you) to replicate the ENTIRE existing/anticipated research workflow, from sample collection through data analysis, so that anyone could follow the full set of steps taken to generate the project dataset/s. Some labs will be able to include more data and documentation/protocols than others, and that is ok.

Assessment of completion

Create a full set of files and cursory descriptions. Organize the files into pipeline format correctly, following one of the listed references and/or documenting deviations from the recommended structure. Include field/lab/other protocols (or references to such) in your pipeline. If you don't have many protocols to reference, note that.

Metadata

Metadata are heavily reliant on documentation. As you are completing implementation tasks in this subsection, document here the steps and references you would need to update metadata for an existing data product, or to create metadata for a future project dataset, including references to any documentation you use. Place key documentation or metadata templates into an Appendix. Also document any questions you have along the way, especially when the meaning of any particular metadata field is unclear.

Assessment of completion

Create a thoughtful procedure demonstrating application of concepts. Include detailed steps. Cite resources used. Reflect: would your lab mate be able to use your procedure to generate metadata for a different data product on this project?

Implementation: data product tasks

*Create results-level and product-level descriptive metadata for your data pipeline research object (aka, data product; data package) using the NSIDC DAAC Data Accession Request Form (^{^ref}), a README, or EDI's Metadata Template (^{^17}), watching *The EDI metadata template_ video* (^{^18}) as needed. In the case that "external" data (i.e., "external" being data you didn't collect) are part of the data product: best practice is to include a copy of the full dataset you retrieved and used in your analyses, but in some instances such as very large datasets, that is impractical. In that instance, be sure to include full citations in your documentation (metadata) to track the provenance (i.e., origin) of all external data. If data were retrieved via browser-based API call or other script-based methods, also document as*

applicable the mode of retrieval: URL or script used, the precise API call, and time and date of data retrieval. Evaluate the metadata you create using at minimum the CURATE(D) checklist /Understand, /Augment, and /Evaluate sections (^15). Write up a short paragraph summarizing your evaluation, highlighting areas that still need work, and keep it with your dataset for further metadata updates.

Now imagine (or expect) that you are going to combine the project's relevant analysis-ready data with additional data, such as LANDSAT data. What additional information or data/metadata might you need to do so? Generate a plan to fill any gaps.

Assessment of completion

Completely fill out the relevant metadata templates with detailed metadata, including related citations. Write a metadata evaluation summary that includes all points. Assess the compatibility of relevant project data/metadata with LANDSAT data/metadata and outline steps to take to ensure project data compatibility goals are met.

Licensing and Public Domain Waivers (i.e., Intellectual Rights)

Copy the "How to Apply a License to Your Data and Code" document (^19) into this section, modifying it by taking the following steps. While completing implementation steps in this section, document any additional steps or questions that arise during the process, including any additional documentation or information that would clarify uncertainties.

Assessment of completion

Copy the intellectual rights document here. Thoughtfully modify the document with additional steps and/or questions that arise in applying licenses and waivers, perhaps adding an FAQ format section. Cite resources used.

Implementation: data product tasks

Use the "How to Apply a License to Your Data and Code" document (^19). Select licenses and/or waivers to apply your project data and code (assuming you have / will have code). Be sure to discuss your selections with data co-creators/authors. Identify where you would document and store your intellectual rights decisions in relation to your data product pipeline.

Assessment of completion

Use appropriate intellectual rights language for both code and data licenses and/or waivers that you select. Openly discuss your selections with project collaborators. Identify where you would store your licensing decisions in relation to your data file organization pipeline.

Data Integrity

After completing the implementation tasks that follow, assess: is there enough information about how snow albedo data were collected by both UAVs and LANDSAT to be able to transform the data for intercomparison? If not, document what you would like to know to be able to compare and/or reuse these data.

Assessment of completion

Provide a thorough data integrity assessment.

Implementation: data product tasks

Consider project data, (and/or the data the project team anticipates collecting). Review Horsburgh's sensor data Table 1 (^{^ref}) suggestions for data integrity flagging. Which of these flags, if any, might be useful to incorporate into the project team's existing data integrity checking processes going forward? Are there any integrity checks not on Horsburgh's Table 1 that would be useful (e.g., LANDSAT data integrity checks and flags)? Are there any non-sensor-specific flags you would add? How is the team documenting data uncertainties? Create a table documenting a preliminary set of data integrity flags that the team already uses or could harmonize to consistently apply across contexts (e.g., field UAV and LANDSAT campaigns, lab analysis, data analysis (whichever context(s) applies/y)). Have a discussion with the project team about the feasibility of implementing any new data integrity measures. Include discussion outcomes in this section.

Assessment of completion

Provide a critical review of Horsburgh's data integrity flags. For sensor data collectors, assess and document usefulness (or questions you might have) on each of Horsburgh's 10 types of error, and relate it to your experience. If LANDSAT data integrity checks and/or flags are available, review them and consider how they might be useful to project team data. If you work with non-sensor data, create a table similar to Horsburgh's (with all 3 columns), including flags that would apply to the data you work with.

Data Modeling

Create an annotated bibliography that points to some (min. 3) helpful resources project members could use to create a data model for project data compatibility goals. Write a paragraph describing how team members might use a data model as project data grow more complex.

Assessment of completion

Identify several useful data modeling resources and annotate or highlight the key lessons/takeaways from each. Document questions as part of a summary paragraph, and provide a thoughtful assessment of whether data models might be useful to this project.

Implementation: data product tasks

Create a simple star schema data model representing the dimensions or variables in a project dataset. Use the star schema discussed in McGill's third commandment ([^]ref) as an example and guide. Review the star schema you generate, and use McGill's example to think about other dimension tables that would make the data more useful / more fully contextualized.

Assessment of completion

Generate a representation of project data with a star schema. Suggest at least two additional dimension tables you would like to see, and list their columns.

Acknowledgements

This material is based upon work supported in part by the National Science Foundation EPSCoR Cooperative Agreement OIA-1757351 and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration EPSCoR Cooperative Agreement 22-22EPSCoR-0006 (MT-80NSSC22M0169). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation or the National Aeronautics and Space Administration.

Appendix I: Policy and Guidance References